

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CHAT-BOT TECHNOLOGY AS A MEANS OF FORMATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCE IN SELF-STUDY

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Abstract

In the context of modern education, independent learning of foreign languages is becoming increasingly important, and chat-bots are one of the effective tools. These technologies provide learners with the opportunity to practice language skills by interacting with artificial intelligence that simulates communication in a foreign language. The article analyzes the main aspects of chat-bots such as interactivity, personalization and adaptation to the learner's level. Their benefits are discussed, including regular practice, automated feedback, and reduced language learning anxiety. Special attention is paid to their impact on the development of written foreign language competence and motivation of high school students.

Keywords: chat-bots; foreign language competence; independent learning; interactive learning; artificial intelligence

Introduction

With the development of digital technologies, independent learning of foreign languages is becoming more and more accessible and effective. One of the key tools in this process are chat-bots, which simulate communication in a foreign language using artificial intelligence. These programs provide learners with the opportunity to practice language skills at any time and in a convenient way, contributing to speech development, vocabulary development and reducing language barriers.

Several foreign educators and researchers have positively commented on the use of chat-bots in language learning, particularly for English. For instance, Fatma Şeyma Koç and Perihan Savaş conducted a systematic meta-synthesis study highlighting the effectiveness of chat-bots for enhancing language skills among learners [1]. Huang, Hew, and Fryer provided a comprehensive review of chat-bot-supported language learning, pointing out the various benefits that these tools offer to students, such as increased engagement and personalized learning experiences [2]. Gulnara Myrzagalieva notes that these technologies create an interactive environment that promotes student motivation and engagement Tatyana Kuznetsova emphasizes that chat-bots provide an opportunity to practice speaking and writing, as well as instant feedback, which is key to the formation of foreign language competence [3;4].

Materials and types of research.

The objectives of this study are: first, to analyze the role of chat-bots in improving grammatical accuracy and sentence structure in students' written work, second, to compare the progress of learners using chat-bots with traditional self-study methods, and third, to identify the most effective chat-bot features that support foreign language competence. The study aims to investigate the effectiveness of chat-bots in developing high school students' written foreign language compe-

tence in the process of independent learning with a focus on improving writing skills, grammatical accuracy, and vocabulary use.

Tools

First, various foreign language learning chat-bots such as "HelloTalk" were selected and analyzed to understand their impact on the development of high school students' writing skills. HelloTalk allows learners to interact with native speakers through text messages and voice recordings, which helps to practice writing and improve communication skills.

Second, questionnaires were designed to collect feedback from learners about their experiences with chat-bots. Questions in the questionnaires focused on usability, motivation, and changes in confidence when writing. Writing samples were collected before and after using the chat-bots to assess changes in grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure, allowing for comparative analysis of student progress.

Third, observations of the learners' use of chat-bots were conducted to capture patterns of interaction, activity and difficulties encountered. Interviews with the learners were organized to gain a deep understanding of their perceptions of chat-bots and to find out the impact of these technologies on their motivation and anxiety levels in writing assignments. These steps helped to collect qualitative data on the impact of chat-bots on learning.

Procedure.

Chat-bot Selection and Implementation:

HelloTalk is one of the chat-bots that is chosen based on user feedback and its features. Once chosen, it is included into the classroom so that students can interact with it and develop their language skills. During this time, observations are done to track student interactions. 1) You get to practice with real native speakers, which is exciting. 2) The app gives you the flexibility to visit whenever you have spare time, with no pressure to set unachievable goals. 3) The built-in language tools are a great way to facilitate communication between users who don't have much language overlap [5].

Data Collection:

In order to get input from high school students about their interactions with the chat-bot, surveys are used for data collection. The survey asks about general satisfaction, perceived skill improvements, and usability. Questions are focused on the effects on motivation, simplicity of use, and efficacy in improving speaking and writing abilities. Furthermore, written samples from students are gathered before and after the encounter for comparative evaluation.

Analysis and Reporting:

After collecting the data, both student feedback and skill improvements are analyzed. The findings are summarized in a report that offers recommendations for educators and ideas for future research, while also encouraging discussions about the role of technology in language learning.

Specifics of grammatical competence development. In methodological literature three main directions of interpretation of grammatical competence can be found in methodological literature: the ability to produce an automated speech action that ensures the correct morphological and syntactic design of a speech unit; the ability to automatically retrieve grammatical means of speech from long-term memory; the ability to use a grammatical form of speech correctly (without errors) [6].

The requirements for the development of grammatical competence of high school students also include the improvement of skills of recognizing and using in speech verbs in the most common temporal forms of the active voice: Present Simple, Future Simple and Past Simple, Present and Past Continuous, Present and Past Perfect; modal verbs and their equivalents. It also provides for the development of knowledge of the signs and skills of recognizing and using in speech verbs in the following forms of the active voice: Present Perfect Continuous and Past Perfect Continuous and the passive voice: Present Simple Passive, Future Simple Passive, Past Simple Passive, Present Perfect Passive, as well as the development of knowledge of the signs and skills of recognizing in reading verbs in Past Perfect Passive, Future Perfect Passive; non-personal forms of the verb (Infinitive, Participle I and Gerund) without distinguishing their functions [7].

Thus, the main task of chat-bots is to solve the problem of repeating grammatical material, which initially almost all potential users mastered in the program of general Kazakh school.

Implementing Chat-bots for English Language Learning: An Experimental Design

In a study conducted with high school students learning English, a role-playing scenario was integrated into the chat-bot HelloTalk. The objective was to enhance conversational skills and cultural understanding by simulating real-life interactions.

1. **Scenario Selection:** Various real-life situations for the role-playing activities were selected, such as ordering food in a restaurant, asking for directions, and making a hotel reservation. These scenarios were chosen to reflect common situations that students might encounter when using English in everyday life.

2. **Preparation:** Before engaging with the chat-bot, students received a brief overview of the vocabulary and phrases relevant to each scenario. This preparatory phase included practice with common expressions, questions, and responses specific to each situation.

3. **Engagement with the Chat-bot:** Students were instructed to initiate conversations with the chat-bot based on the selected scenarios. For example, in the restaurant scenario, students might start the conversation by greeting the chat-bot as the waiter, saying, "Hello! I would like to see the menu, please." The chat-bot would respond in kind, providing a simulated dialogue that guided students through the conversation.

4. **Feedback and Reflection:** After completing the role-play, students received instant feedback from the chat-bot. If they made grammatical errors or used incorrect vocabulary, the chat-bot provided corrections and suggestions. This feedback loop was crucial for reinforcing learning and helping students understand their mistakes.

5. **Discussion and Improvement:** Following the role-play, students participated in a group discussion led by the teacher. They reflected on their experiences, shared challenges they faced during the interaction, and discussed effective strategies for improving their conversational skills in real-life situations.

Research results

20 high-school students of "Hilondon" English centre in Uralsk, Kazakhstan took part in this study. When asked about the frequency of chat-bots use, 24.4% used chat-bots frequently, 76.6% used it occasionally. About 65% of the students indicated that their speaking ability had improved as a result of constant interaction with chat-bots, and 45% expressed increased confidence in their ability to communicate in English. About 70% of the respondents felt that the instant feedback provided by the chat-bots helped them to correct mistakes and better understand language rules. When asked about their overall satisfaction with the experience of using chat-bots, 82% of students rated it positively, citing accessibility and convenience as the main benefits..

Advantages of HelloTalk, the most important, according to students:

- engaging in conversations with native speakers enhances fluency and comprehension.
- opportunities to learn about different cultures and language nuances.
- easy to navigate, allowing students to focus on learning.
- features like translation tools and pronunciation assistance support various learning styles.
- immediate corrections from native speakers help build confidence.

Some students noted problems with the quality of conversations, as not all users are able to give accurate corrections or constructive feedback. In addition, reliance on peer conversations can sometimes lead to the dissemination of incorrect information or use of language. Privacy issues have also been raised as students communicate with strangers, which can lead to security

issues or uncomfortable exchanges. In addition, the design of the app may be too complex for some users, especially those who are unfamiliar with technology, which may hinder their learning. Finally, while real-time feedback is useful, it may not always be as comprehensive and structured as advice from professional instructors.

Conclusion

We can conclude that the dynamic and fast-paced lifestyle of modern man generates the need for new learning formats in which the learner can independently determine the time that can be allocated to study the material. The use of chat-bots responds to this trend: the user can devote a few minutes a day and study all the material gradually or turn to certain topics. A promising direction for further research is the possibility of personalizing learning through the use of automated individual trajectories, as well as the description of the use of this technology for the development of students' lexical competence. Since the functionality of modern services for developing chat-bots allows users to enter answers through voice dialing, one of the directions of development of the above-described technology can be considered to provide the introduction and activation of language units (both grammatical constructions and lexical units) in students' oral speech.

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